

Supplementary material

Simulation to test the ZAG models ability to cope with zeros in the data

We performed simulation tests to explore the ability of the ZAG model to cope with the proportion of zeros in the data set (23 % and 30 % zeros for the total and sessile young lice, respectively) and compared the observed versus expected values from the final ZAG model. The model was able to cope with the zeros (21 % and 28 % zeros were the modes in the simulation output, for the total and sessile young lice, respectively, Appendix Fig. I), but showed a compressed set of expected values (up to about 1.5 lice g^{-1}) compared to the observed values, where a small number of fish had extremely high level of infestations (up to 9.1 lice g^{-1}) (Appendix Fig. II).

Appendix Fig. I. Percentage of zeros in the data (red dot) and in n=1000 simulated data sets, for the total number of lice (upper panel) and young sessile stages of lice (lower).

Appendix Fig. II. Observed versus expected (from n=1000 simulated data sets, ZAG model) values of lice per gram fish. Upper panel shows the total number of lice and lower panel shows sessile young lice.

Model output for Bernoulli and Gamma models

The ZAG model produces separate results for the Bernoulli (presence or absence of lice) and Gamma (positive number of lice). These results are presented in Appendix Figs. III-VIII.

Bernoulli model (for presence or absence of lice)

Appendix Fig. III. Probability of having lice on fish at different *Lice Infestation Pressures*.

Output shows Bernoulli part (presence/absence of lice) from INLA model, for total number of lice and young sessile lice (upper and lower panels, respectively).

Appendix Fig. IV. Probability of having lice on fish at different levels of *Current*. Output shows Bernoulli part (presence/absence of lice) from INLA model, for total number of lice and young sessile lice (upper and lower panels, respectively).

Appendix Fig. V. Probability of having lice on fish at different levels of *Salinity*. Output shows Bernoulli part (presence/absence of lice) from INLA model, for total number of lice and young sessile lice (upper and lower panels, respectively).

Gamma model (for positive values of lice)

Appendix Fig. VI. Observed (dots) and predicted (INLA model, line with 95 % confidence band) number of salmon lice per gram of sea trout at different *Lice Infestation Pressure* in the environment, for total number of lice and young sessile lice (upper and lower panels, respectively).

Appendix Fig. VII. Observed (dots) and predicted (INLA model, line with 95 % confidence band) number of salmon lice per gram of sea trout at different *Current* strengths in the environment, for total number of lice and young sessile lice (upper and lower panels, respectively).

Appendix Fig. VIII. Observed (dots) and predicted (INLA model, line with 95 % confidence band) number of salmon lice per gram of sea trout at different *Salinity* levels in the environment, for total number of lice and young sessile lice (upper and lower panels, respectively).

Cross validation

We ran a series of cross-validation tests (with a linear mixed effects model – *lmer* in R):

$\text{Log}(\text{Lice infestation} + 1) \sim \text{Lice Infestation Pressure} + \text{Current} + \text{Salinity}, \text{Site} = \text{random}$

using the R-package *groupdata2*. Random sampling of 80 % ('training set') of the data leaving the last 20 % of the data as a 'testing set' was done with the **fold()** function in package *groupdata2*. The training- and testing-sets rotate for each fold used (n = 5).

We explored whether single or few *Sites* was able to drive the main trends. There were no clear geographical trends, e.g. from south to north in the parameter estimates for any of the explanatory variables, *Lice Infestation Pressure*, *Current*, *Salinity*, although a few sites deviated from the others (Appendix Figs. IX-XI). Model parameters from the *lmer*-model showed a significant negative effect of *Salinity* (Appendix Fig. XI). The same trend was found but was not significant in the ZAG model. The cross-validation confirmed our results from the ZAG model.

Parameter estimates for each Site

Appendix Fig. IX. Separate parameter estimates for *Lice Infestation Pressure*, for all 40 localities. Model output from *lmer* model. Localities are sorted from south to north along the coast.

Appendix Fig. X. Separate parameter estimates for *Current*, for all 40 localities. Model output from *Imer* model. Localities are sorted from south to north along the coast.

Appendix Fig. XI. Separate parameter estimates for *Salinity*, for all 40 localities. Model output from *Imer* model. Localities are sorted from south to north along the coast.